

SHORT NOTES

**On the Kinetics of Calcium Exchange from Ca-soil by
Ammonium and Potassium Chlorides in
Aqueous Solution***

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Among the exchangeable bases, calcium plays the most important role in edaphology. Several Soil textbooks¹ have dealt adequately on the factors which influence the exchange of soil calcium. Since time is also an important factor in the exchange of calcium in different soil media, its kinetic study, which has not yet appeared in literature, may be a matter of interesting observation.

In the present study, two neutral salts, viz., ammonium and potassium chlorides, have been taken to study the kinetics of calcium exchange from three calcium soils prepared by treating for different times ($\frac{1}{2}$ hr. soil A; 2 hr. soil B; 8 hr. soil C) a Gangetic alluvium soil with normal calcium chloride solution, washing with chemically pure water, and finally drying with anhydrous ethanol (20 ml $\times$ 2). The three experimental soils (A, B, and C) contained, respectively, 18.62, 23.12, and 25.12 m.e. of total exchangeable calcium per 100 g. soil.

TABLE I

	Time of exchange.				$\Sigma k/2^2 \text{min}^{-1}$.
	15 min.	30 min.	45 min.	60 min.	
A. Exchange of calcium with <i>N</i> -NH ₄ Cl.					
I. Soil A.					
Ex. Ca (m.e.)	2.10	4.20	6.20	6.71	1.20×10^{-3}
<i>k</i>	0.01116	0.01215	0.01341	0.01128	
II. Soil B.					
Ex. Ca (m.e.)	2.35	4.61	6.95	7.55	7.10×10^{-3}
<i>k</i>	0.00695	0.00716	0.00778	0.00652	
III. Soil C.					
Ex. Ca (m.e.)	2.45	4.72	7.17	7.62	6.62×10^{-3}
<i>k</i>	0.00635	0.00689	0.00730	0.00594	
B. Exchange of calcium with <i>N</i> -KCl.					
I. Soil A.					
Ex. Ca (m.e.)	1.96	3.82	5.75	6.20	1.07×10^{-3}
<i>k</i>	0.00990	0.01073	0.01216	0.01005	
II. Soil B.					
Ex. Ca (m.e.)	2.00	3.92	5.92	6.47	5.91×10^{-3}
<i>k</i>	0.00574	0.00607	0.00649	0.00536	
III. Soil C.					
Ex. Ca (m.e.)	2.06	4.00	5.98	6.48	5.37×10^{-3}
<i>k</i>	0.00513	0.00551	0.00599	0.00487	

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1. Russell, "Soil Conditions and Plant Growth", 1961; Bear, "Chemistry of the Soil", 1954.

The results in Table I show that with the increase of time of exchange, there is no proportionate increase in the amount of exchangeable calcium; its amount is therefore directed by the total exchangeable calcium of the experimental soil. The phenomenon can therefore be defined by the following simple relation:

$$dx/dt = k(X-x) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where X = the total exchangeable calcium, x = exchangeable calcium obtained at a particular interval of time, and k = the specific exchangeable rate of calcium,

On rearrangement of equation (1), integration, and other necessary mathematical operations, the value of k may be obtained from the relation:

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{X}{X-x} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The different k values calculated have been shown in Table I. It may be observed that for soil A, the specific exchangeable rate of calcium is of the order 10^{-2} and this value decreases to 10^{-3} with B and C. For a particular soil, the order thus appears to be independent of the nature of salts used to exchange calcium. The orders also show that the specific exchangeable rate of calcium decreases with increasing amounts of total exchangeable calcium. In other words, the true exchangeable coefficient of calcium, K , can be obtained from the relation:

$$X = K. 1/k.$$

TABLE II

Relation between exchangeable coefficients and total exchangeable calcium.

Soil.	By NH_4Cl .	Total ex. Ca (m.e./100 g.).	By KCl .	$\Sigma K/3$ (m.e. min $^{-1}$). By NH_4Cl . KCl .	$\Sigma[\Sigma K/3]_{0.5}$ (m.e., min $^{-1}$).
A	1.20×10^{-2} (1)	13.62	1.07×10^{-2} (1)	1.65 $\times 10^{-1}$	1.40 $\times 10^{-1}$
	1.63×10^{-1} (2)		1.46×10^{-1} (2)		
B	7.10×10^{-3} (1)	23.12	5.91×10^{-3} (1)		
	1.64×10^{-1} (2)		1.36×10^{-1} (2)		
C	6.62×10^{-3} (1)	25.12	5.37×10^{-3} (1)		
	1.66×10^{-1} (2)		1.35×10^{-1} (2)		

N.B.—(1) and (2) denote respectively k min $^{-1}$ and K m.e. min $^{-1}$.

In Table II, the values of $\Sigma K/3$ in both the salts is of the order of 10^{-1} and is not much different from $\Sigma[\Sigma K/3]_{0.5}$. This latter value being independent of every variable

considered in the present experiments, is thus more of universal nature and may be incorporated in equation (2) in the manner:

$$\frac{1.52 \times 10^{-1}}{X} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{X}{(X-x)} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

which may be rearranged as follows to provide a relation with the exchangeable soil calcium to be obtained after certain interval of time:

$$x = X - \text{anti log} \left\{ \log_{10} X - \left[\frac{t}{2.303} \cdot \frac{1.52 \times 10^{-1}}{X} \right] \right\} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

The validity of relation (4) is being considered with other neutral salts in presence of different kinds of soils; the results will be reported later.

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